

RECYCLING OF AUTOMOTIVE SHEET METAL-FIBRE REINFORCED PLASTIC-HYBRID STRUCTURES

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Keywords: *Automotive lightweight design, Multi-material system, Hybrid structure, Fiber reinforced plastic, Prepreg, Prepreg press technology, Recycling*

Abstract

Current research work at the Chair for Automotive Lightweight Construction (LiA) at the University of Paderborn concentrates on the investigation of hybrid materials, their processing and their mechanical properties. In particular, new manufacturing processes like the prepreg press technology are developed to make hybrid components attractive and available for automotive mass production. Another point of research deals with the recycling of hybrid structures. Especially for automotive structures this is an important point because vehicles should be recyclable after their life cycle with a rate of nearly 100 %.

This paper focusses on basic investigations on hybrid materials consisting of sheet metal and FRP. The prepreg press technology allows the manufacturing of hybrid structures for example for automotive applications with cycle times of less than five minutes. The bonding is realized by the use of the epoxy resin as an adhesive.

Another important issue is the recycling of hybrid automotive structures. Here, a new approach was developed. The components are locally heated by inductive or resistance heating equipment. This can be realized without cutting a single component from the rest of the vehicle. By the influence of heat the epoxy resin of the FRP as well as the adhesive bonding is affected. After this step the FRP reinforcement can easily be removed from the sheet metal and recycled e. g. by a pyrolysis process. In the end of the recycling process fibers and sheet metal are obtained.

To evaluate the separation of the sheet metal and the FRP component test specimens are heated by resistance heating equipment. A furnace heating is taken into account as a reference. For the resistance heating the specimens are provided with two

terminal contacts to realize a current flow through the component. The electric resistance leads to a heating up of the sheet metal. The inductive as well as the resistance heating are able to realize very high heating rates of above 100 K/s. Shear tensile tests are used to characterize the strength of the adhesive bonding after the heating.

1 Introduction

To meet the objectives of climate protection in the automotive industry, innovative and holistic approaches of lightweight design need to be found. For example, by reducing the vehicle weight by 100 kg, a reduction of CO₂ emissions of about 8.5 g/km respectively a reduction of fuel consumption of about 0.3 l/100 km can be realized. Nevertheless the average weight of automobiles increased over the past years mainly because of safety and comfort requirements.

One upcoming method to reduce the vehicle weight is the use of sheet metal-fiber reinforced plastic-hybrid structures in high loaded areas, such as in the upper region of B-Pillars. In order to reach the recycling requirements of the governments, a method to separate the sheet metal and the reinforced plastic has to be generated during the recycling-process.

2 State of the Art

2.1 Automotive Lightweight Construction

In the automotive lightweight construction, three main trends are obvious: lightweight design is realized either by using high-strength metal alloys, or by substituting for example metals for composites or by combining different materials.

Using high-strength metal alloys offers the opportunity to reduce the wall thickness of structures. However, once a critical minimum

thickness is reached, the designers can expect stability problems. Thus, the potential of high-strength materials for light weight construction is limited by the stiffness.

Second, substituting conventional construction materials with carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) allows considerable weight savings [1] [2] of about 50 % compared to current solutions consisting of steel. At the moment FRP-structures are predominantly used for high-priced vehicles because of the expensive material and processing. Main challenges for the automotive industry are to reduce the high costs of processing these materials, to manufacture FRP-structures and to integrate FRP into existing processes.

Hence, structural components realized in multi-material design are an interesting alternative. They consist of a combination of, for example, steel and FRP [3] [4]. Two approaches can be distinguished. The high stiffness of the so called “Erlanger Beam” is achieved by reinforcing a thin-walled steel structure with short fibre reinforced plastic ribs by means of form closure. Depending on the vehicle, this method can save between 0.3 kg and 0.5 kg only in the roof frame [5]. The second approach constitutes a combination of highest-strength steel and continuous fibre reinforced plastics. In order to increase the overall strength of the components, steel and FRP are bonded tightly across a large area. This design should allow manufacturers to produce safety-relevant vehicle components, such as B-pillars, at lower costs compared to a mere CFRP design. Using such material for a B-pillar, 6 kg per vehicle or up to 35 % of the weight could be saved [6] [7]. Due to the tight bonding between both single materials, these are also called hybrid materials.

2.2 Challenges of Multi-Material-Structures

One main disadvantage of today’s multi-material systems is among other things the processing. This is predominantly manual or only partially automated. The three most commonly used joining methods are welding [8], riveting [9] and bonding [10]. All of them necessitate an additional time and cost consuming process step. These disadvantages shall be overcome with the production of hybrid materials by the prepreg press technology and the use of the matrix resin as an adhesive. Thus multi-material components of highest strength can be produced in large volumes. Especially for automotive structures,

the recycling is an important point because vehicles should be recyclable after their life cycle with a rate of nearly 100 %. At the moment there is no holistic concept for the recycling of these components available.

3 Sheet metal-FRP-Hybrid Structures

Current research work at the Chair for Automotive Lightweight Construction (LiA) at the University of Paderborn concentrates on the investigation of hybrid materials, their processing and their mechanical properties.

Hybrid materials consist of a sheet metal basic layer, a locally applied FRP reinforcement layer and an optional sheet metal covering layer. The layered structure offers the possibility to tailor components to their expected loading (Figure 1). Such tailored structures do not only bear a high potential for lightweight design but also show an optimized use of the expensive FRP materials, which finally leads to cost-optimized lightweight constructions. The sandwich structure of hybrid materials increases the stiffness especially of area measured components. Amongst others press hardened steels can be used as sheet metals. Due to the FRP reinforcements, a significant reduction of the wall thickness of the steel parts is possible. Hybrid components can easily be integrated into existing processes of vehicle production, because their metallic surface enables the use of conventional joining technologies like spot welding or clinching. The integration into existing body constructions is also possible.

Fig. 1 Load adapted hybrid structure

4 Prepreg Press Technology

The prepreg press technology is one approach to produce hybrid structural automotive parts in large volumes. The process can be divided into four main parts (Figure 2). First, prepregs (pre-impregnated, semi-finished fibre products) are produced continuously on special machines and shipped on coils. The layer structure is realised according to the expected loads in the component, for example a B-pillar. The laminate is cut corresponding to the later structure geometry. Second, a robot handles the prepregs. After inserting an already formed steel structure into a heated steel tool, the prepreg is applied to the steel structure by automated handling. Then the tailored prepreg is pressed onto the sheet metal by a heated punch. As the epoxy resin functions as an adhesive the joining of sheet metal and CFRP is realised in this third step, too. After a pre-curing of about 90 to 120 seconds, depending on the thickness of the prepreg, the hybrid component is removed by a robot and stacked. The post-curing of the components is realised during a downstream cathaphoretic painting process.

Fig. 2 Process of prepreg press technology

5 Bonding of Sheet Metal and CFRP

5.1 Materials and Testing Methods

The joining technology between CFRP and sheet metal is a decisive factor for the functioning and strength of hybrid materials. In order to characterize the joining properties single lap-shear specimens were investigated according to DIN EN 1465:2009. For the investigation four different joining technologies were used: a) epoxy resin matrix as adhesive, b) adhesive Dow Betamate 1620, c) blind rivets and d) thread cutting screws (Figure 3).

Fig. 3 Shear tensile test specimens

The specimens consisted of sheet metal and CFRP. For the metal component a S235JR with a thickness of $t = 2$ mm was used. The prepregs were standard semi-finished products from SGL. The epoxy resin from SGL (Type E201) embeds carbon fibres in a symmetric 9 layer bidirectional scrim (0/90/0/90/0/90/0/90/0°). The prepregs were manufactured by prepreg press technology as described in chapter 4. For the bonding with epoxy resin as an adhesive the prepreg was directly pressed on the metallic surface. The CFRP of the samples joined by Dow Betamate 1620, blind rivetting (Gesipa PolyGrip 6.4 x 15 mm) and thread cutting screws (DIN 7513 M4 x 10 mm) were first pressed and cured. Afterwards the CFRP was joined onto the sheet metal.

To find an optimum solution of the conflict between economical aims and the strength of the joint time, temperature for consolidation during the prepreg-press process was varied according to the reaction-velocity temperature rule (Arrhenius equation). The temperature was varied between 120 °C and 200 °C. The prepreg-pressed samples were compared with adhesive-bonded samples and the influence of different types of surface treatment was investigated.

5.2 Results and Discussion

A comparison of maximum force and tensile energy absorption of the different joining technologies is shown in Figure 4. The epoxy resin matrix reaches slightly smaller values than the Dow Betamate for both parameters. The advantage of the use of the epoxy resin as an adhesive is, that the complex and cost intensive joining process can be omitted. The values for the mechanical fasteners are significantly worse because of high stress concentration at the joining element. This leads to failure of the CFRP.

Fig. 4 Comparison of maximum force and tensile energy absorption of different bonding technologies for hybrid structures

The analysis of failure behaviour of the different bonding technologies showed some characteristics (Figure 5).

While for the pressed samples failure occurred in between the boundary layer and the second fiber layer of the CFRP, the adhesive-bonded samples failed due to delamination of the first fiber layer. The joint area itself remained undamaged. The mechanical fasteners were predominantly pulled out of the CFRP component.

The fiber orientation of the boundary layer had the greatest influence on the properties of the joint (Figure 6). Samples with fibres vertical to the direction of loading (90°) had the highest strength. The elastic matrix material dominated the mechanical properties close to the boundary layer. The fibres only bear a small part of the load. Thus, the laminate can absorb local tension peaks like a bond line. Samples with fibres parallel to loading, in the contacted layer, failed with 75 % of the load applied.

Fig. 5 Characteristic failure behavior of different bonding technologies

Fig. 6 Influence of fiber orientation of the contacted layer on the bond strength

The inhomogeneous structure of CFRP is reflected in the properties of the joint. Special properties of such materials need to be considered in the design of hybrid structures in order to achieve the intended properties of the compound.

6 Recycling of Hybrid Structures

In the last decades the variety of the applied materials in automotive construction has raised significantly. On the other hand ambitious efforts have emerged to regain these materials. This is a consequence of increasing costs for raw materials and energy, ecological awareness or legal requirements. For example a regulation in the European Union orders that an increasing percentage by weight of an end-of-life vehicle has to be recycled.

Today there is no integrated concept available for achieving these high recycling rates concerning the multi-material structures of modern cars. Thus, an important challenge is to find potentials to separate the components of hybrid structures consisting of sheet metal and FRP.

Here a new approach is described. The components can locally be heated by inductive or resistance heating equipment. This can be realized without cutting a single component from the rest of the vehicle. By the influence of heat the epoxy resin of the FRP as well as the adhesive bonding is affected. After this step the FRP reinforcement can easily be removed from the sheet metal and recycled e. g. by a pyrolysis process. In the end of the recycling process fibers and sheet metal are obtained.

To evaluate the separation of the sheet metal and the FRP component test specimens are heated by resistance heating equipment. A furnace heating is taken into account as a reference.

6.1 Materials and Testing Methods

For the recycling experiments one combination of sheet metal and FRP is chosen. For the sheet metal the DD11 steel with a tensile strength of 440 MPa is used. This steel is primarily applied in stress loaded components with complex geometries. For the investigations the same prepreg material as described in chapter 5.1 was used.

The hybrid structure is made with the prepreg press technology (Chapter 4). Therefore, the sheet metal with a thickness of 2 mm is cut into pieces of 100 mm x 150 mm. A cut of the CFRP with the same length and width is laid on the steel. Both parts are placed in a heated sheet die for a time of 120 s at a temperature of 180 °C and a pressure of 0.3 MPa. The post-curing was realized in a furnace for 30 minutes at a temperature of 180 °C, which simulates the cataphoretic dip painting process.

Afterwards specimens (Figure 7) are cut out of the structure with a length of 120 mm and a width of 20 mm. At both ends the CFRP is removed for contacting the steel with an electric current to realize a current flow through the component.

These specimens were heated up to different temperatures by resistance heating and furnace heating as the reference in order to separate the materials. For lower temperatures the adhesive bonding obviously was not affected. To quantify the remaining bond strength, shear tensile tests were performed. For these tests two grooves were cut into the specimen, which results in a defined joint zone.

Fig. 7 Specimen before and after preparation for shear tensile tests

The tool for separating the FRP from the steel (Figure 8) by resistance heating consists of two steel bases. Above each two plates made of copper are screwed together with the base. In between the specimen is clamped. The copper is cable-connected with a power source. This generator is a modified device originally used for welding, which gives out a high amperage with a low voltage. The whole equipment is put on a ceramic plate due to electric insulation. Figure 9 shows the used experimental setup.

Fig. 8 Schematic illustration of the experimental setup for resistance heating

Fig. 9 Experimental setup

6.2 Results and Discussion

The first experimental series is the furnace heating. Therefore specimens are put into a furnace for 1 and 5 minutes at the temperatures 180 °C, 200°C,

220 °C, 300°C and 400°C. In a furnace the heat is mainly transferred to the specimens by thermal radiation what leads comparatively low heating rates. After cooling-down they are prepared for shear tensile tests (Figure 7). These tests are used to characterize the strength of the adhesive bonding after the heating. The bonding strengths against different temperatures for the heating processes are shown in Figure 10.

Fig. 10 Bonding strength for different temperatures and heating technologies

While the untreated hybrid structures reach a shear tensile strength of about 25 MPa at room temperature (Chapter 5), the heated specimens show decreasing shear tensile strengths at increasing heating temperatures. The specimens heated at a temperature of 400°C for 5 minutes reach 30 % of the bond strength compared to the untreated specimens. A short heating for only 1 minute has no significant influence.

In the second experimental series the specimens are heated by resistance heating. The electric resistance of the material leads to a heating up of the sheet metal as a consequence of the Joule effect. For constant profile sections the heat can be reached very homogenous (Figure 11). This technique is for example used for resistance spot welding and allows very high heating rates of above 100 K/s.

Fig. 11 Infrared camera picture of a specimen while resistance heating

For the resistance heating similar temperatures are chosen as for the furnace heating (220°C, 250 °C, 300°C, 370 °C, 400°C and 500 °C). Within a few seconds the specimen has reached the intended temperature. At all temperatures the FRP drops down or can easily be removed afterwards e. g. with the fingertips (?). The results are shown in figure 10. Shear tensile tests are not possible any longer. In figure 12 the surface of the sheet metal of a specimen after the resistance heating is shown. There are no attachments of the epoxy resin identifiable.

Fig. 12 Specimen after resistance heating without attachments of the epoxy resin

7 Conclusions

In this paper it can be shown that heating a hybrid structure has a remarkable effect on the strength of the adhesive bonding. While the temperature increases the bonding strengths after cooling-down are decreasing.

Additionally, it is visible that higher heating rates of the resistance heating compared to the rates of furnace heating result in significant lower bonding strengths. Furthermore, there is no bonding at all at a temperature of 200°C and more as the FRP drops down.

One explanation of this effect might be the thermal expansion of the steel. The explicitly higher heating rates of the resistance heating lead to a quick extension of the sheet metal while the FRP component holds a lower temperature in the first instance and is only slightly warming by thermal conduction. In addition, the thermal expansion of CFRP is much lower than the properties of metallic material. These effects might lead the adhesion forces to break up and let the FRP component drop off.

In future research it is necessary to examine and verify these effects by microscopic tests of the specimens and extend the tests to other geometries and construction components like a CFRP reinforced B-pillar.

Summarizing, the concept of a defined, partial heat treatment of sheet metal-FRP hybrid structures is one promising approach to separate bonded automotive components. By this a recycling of multi-material structures is realizable in large series with comparatively low efforts.

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